

Deliverable 3.4: Invited lectures on specific topics

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
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Executive summary

To minimize communication barriers between clinicians and scientists and to expand insights into the research landscape for students, reputed clinicians and scientific researchers will be invited to scientific meetings organized by BMC SAV to give keynote lectures on particular topics (e.g. colon, pancreatic cancer, neuroendocrine tumours, advanced cell culture technologies). In October / November 2020, the lecture series will start with three experts of Ramón y Cajal University Hospital Health Research Institute represented by Servicio Madrilenio de Salud, (SERMAS). Due to the coronavirus pandemic situation the start of this task is delayed.

1 Description of work & main achievements

Reputed clinicians and scientific researchers have been defined to give keynote lectures during scientific online meetings organized by BMC SAV.

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation some tasks of the project are delayed. Therefore, no key note lectures have taken place so far. However, fixed topics have already been defined and the invited speakers have agreed to the invitation.

In October / November 2020, three experts of Ramón y Cajal University Hospital Health Research Institute represented by Servicio Madrilenio de Salud, (SERMAS) will give online lectures. Following speakers and the topic of the keynotes are listed

Key note lecture 1 – 14.10.2020:

Invited expert: Dr Alfredo Carrato

Topic of the lecture: **Future approaches of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma**

Key note lecture 2 – 28.10.2020:

Invited expert: Dr Laura Garcia Bermejo

Topic of the lecture: **Molecular and Cellular mechanisms/biomarkers in PDAC**

Key note lecture 3 - 11.11.2020:

Invited expert: Dr Julie Earl

Topic of the lecture: **Advances in familial pancreatic cancer**

The exact topics of the lectures in 2021 will be determined during the next consortium meeting in March 2021. It is already clear that experts from Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung e.V. (FhG), Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon (NKUA), and Norsk Institutt for Luftforskning Stiftelse (NILU) will give lectures on specific topics relevant for the project VISION (e.g. colon, pancreatic cancer, neuroendocrine tumours, advanced cell culture technologies, nanotechnologies and nanomedicine).

All keynote lectures in 2020 and 2021 will be realized as webinars.

2 Deviation from the workplan

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation the task „invited lectures“ is delayed. But the coordinator and all project partners plan to organize more lectures in 2021 to compensate the delay within the project duration.

3 Conclusion

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation, no key note lectures have taken place so far. However, invited experts agreed to the invitation. The lecture session will start in October 2020 as webinar.